

Subject 1: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis on Risk Factors for Sporadic Food-Borne Illnesses

Part V: Listeriosis

Ursula Gonzales-Barron and Vasco Cadavez
CIMO Mountain Research Centre, School of Agriculture, Polytechnic Institute of Braganza,
Portugal

On request from the French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health and Safety (ANSES) in coordination with Pauline Kooh and Moez Sanaa

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The quality assessment stage was passed by 12 primary studies investigating sporadic listeriosis, which were conducted between 1985 and 2013. From these, seven case-control studies investigated exposures in the non-perinatal population – comprising immunocompromised and elderly, while six case-control studies focused on the broad susceptible population with no distinction between perinatal and non-perinatal cases. These primary studies provided 227 ORs categorised for meta-analysis, being 84% of the meta-analytical data produced by case-control studies from USA (4), UK (2), Australia (1) and Germany (1). Four case-control studies employed a matched experimental design and produced a total of 103 matched ORs. One-hundred and twenty-seven reported ORs were not adjusted by any confounder, while 100 ORs were adjusted by using either Mantel-Haenzel method or logistic regressions. The unconditional and conditional logistic methods were the most widely used models, producing 169 OR measures. After methodological quality assessment, three case-control studies were marked as being below standards, which yielded a total of 16 potentially-biased ORs. With regards to the risk factor classes, sporadic illness investigations focused more on the multiple pathways of exposure (168 ORs) than on host specific factors (59).

According to this meta-analysis study, the most important risk factors in the susceptible population for acquiring listeriosis are: suffering from a chronic disease (overall OR=7.52; 95% CI: 4.57 – 12.35), other medical conditions (overall OR=5.77; 95% CI: 3.85 – 8.62) and recent use of antacids (overall OR=4.01; 95% CI: 2.54 – 6.33). Living on a farm (overall OR=3.29; 95% CI: 1.05 – 10.38) bear greater risk of transmission of listeriosis among the susceptible population than the overall routes of exposure related to foods (overall OR=1.63; 95% CI: 1.36 – 1.94). The ranking of food subcategories as sources of listeriosis is common to the general susceptible population and the non-perinatal population subset. Among the

potential food vehicles of transmission, seafood-based RTE products bear the greatest risk of listeriosis in the general susceptible population (overall OR=3.47; 95% CI: 1.78 – 6.78) and in the non-perinatal population subset (overall OR=7.22; 95% CI: 3.48 – 14.97); conveying a significantly higher risk of transmission than dairy foods such as milk and dairy fats (overall OR=3.25; 95% CI: 2.07 – 5.11; and overall OR=3.31; 95% CI: 1.98 – 5.53, respectively) and cheese (overall OR=2.81; 95% CI: 1.93 – 4.12; and overall OR=2.94; 95% CI: 1.86 – 4.65, respectively). In the broad susceptible population, fish and processed fish (overall OR=2.66; 95% CI: 1.14 – 6.18), molluscs (overall OR=2.15; 95% CI: 0.66 – 6.99) and undercooked poultry (overall OR=1.98; 95% CI: 1.53 – 2.54) present, on average, a higher association with listeriosis than dairy-based RTE foods (overall OR=1.86; 95% CI: 1.30 – 2.67), composite dishes mostly prepared outside the home (overall OR=1.75; 95% CI: 0.96 – 3.19), and composite RTE foods (overall OR=1.42; 95% CI: 0.68 – 2.97). Interestingly, fresh fruits and salads, consumed by the general susceptible (overall OR=1.57; 95% CI: 1.06 – 2.32) and the non-perinatal population subset (overall OR=1.54; 95% CI: 0.76 – 3.10), emerged as a vehicle of transmission of listeriosis, at least as important as processed meats (overall OR=1.39; 95% CI: 1.13 – 1.70; and overall OR=1.53; 95% CI: 1.23 – 1.91, respectively) and meat-based RTE products (overall OR=1.22; 95% CI: 0.81 – 1.84; and overall OR=1.33; 95% CI: 0.87 – 2.03, respectively).

The food pathways of exposure that on meta-analysis have either weak or non-significant association with listeriosis in the general susceptible population and the non-perinatal susceptible population are: vegetables (overall OR=1.10; 95% CI: 0.85 – 1.44; and overall OR=0.92; 95% CI: 0.61 – 1.38, respectively), red meats (overall OR=0.99; 95% CI: 0.81 – 1.21; and overall OR=1.01; 95% CI: 0.80 – 1.26, respectively), produce-based RTE foods (overall OR=1.06; 95% CI: 0.56 – 2.01; and overall OR=1.05; 95% CI: 0.60 – 1.83, respectively) and crustaceans (overall OR=0.91; 95% CI: 0.31 – 2.66). Separate meta-analyses on the effects of handling and setting on the pooled ORs estimated that, on average, susceptible people who had consumed fruits and became ill were 2.358 times (95% CI: 1.297 – 3.622 in Table 11) more likely to have that prepared in a food establishment than those who consumed fruits but did not get ill. Furthermore, susceptible people who consumed raw processed meats or undercooked poultry had their odds of acquiring listeriosis increased by 2.168 (95% CI: 1.297 – 3.622). Very limited or no data were available for travel, animal-contact, person-to-person, and food subcategories such as eggs, grains and beverages, so the significance of these sources as potential vehicles of transmission of listeriosis could not be appraised.

3. Results

3.5 *Listeria monocytogenes*

3.5.1 *Descriptive statistics*

In the systematic review of risk factors pertaining to human infection with listeriosis, a total of 1902 bibliographic sources were initially identified using the keywords in the five search engines. After screening titles and abstracts for relevance, only 189 references remained. Following reading of full papers and assessment of methodology quality, a total of 34 articles were found to meet the requirements for inclusion (Figure 1). Of these, twenty-two fully-documented case-control studies investigated the source(s) of outbreaks and were kept in the JabRef file as their data can be readily extracted. The other twelve case-control studies focused on sporadic disease, and those were the ones included in the present meta-analysis (Figure 1). These published studies were conducted between 1985 and 2013. Table 1 summarises the main features of the case-control studies used in this meta-analysis.

The eligible studies jointly furnished 227 odds-ratios which were categorised for meta-analysis. A total of 27 ORs were retrieved from 4 case-control studies performed before the year 2000, while 200 ORs were excerpted from 8 case-control studies performed after 2000. The majority of primary studies investigated listeriosis caused by undifferentiated serotypes, except for Varma et al. (2007) whose case patients were infected with either serotype 1/2a or 4b. The countries whose case-control studies presented the largest body of results for sporadic listeriosis were Australia (1 study, 72 ORs), USA (4 studies, 56 ORs), Germany (1 study, 36 ORs) and UK (2 studies, 27 ORs) which produced all together ~84% of the ORs retrieved (Figure 2, top left). Regarding the target population, seven case-control studies investigated risk factors of listeriosis in the non-perinatal population, which comprised the immunocompromised and elderly (producing 139 ORs), whereas only one study (Dalton et al., 2011) conducted a case-control investigation on the perinatal population (25 ORs extracted). In six case-control studies, there was no such a distinction, and the perinatal and non-perinatal cases (immunocompromised/elderly) were pooled. This population class was labelled as “perinatal/non-perinatal”, and consisted of 63 ORs. Because the amount of data for the perinatal population was limited, separate meta-analysis models could not be adjusted for this population class. However, separate meta-analyses could be fitted for the non-perinatal population which consisted of people older than 60 years and those suffering from a range of underlying medical conditions. Furthermore, to obtain pooled ORs that could be representative of the entire (susceptible) population, meta-analysis models were adjusted to the combined non-perinatal, perinatal and perinatal/non-perinatal data, as in fact, all of these population types belong to an overarching susceptible class (Figure 2, top right).

In all of the primary studies, the cases of listeriosis were laboratory-confirmed. Four case-control studies (56%) employed a matched experimental design and produced a total of 103 matched ORs. While 91 ORs were computed in univariate analysis, only 12 were obtained in univariate analysis. ORs from matched designs were mostly estimated using CL (56) and UL (27) and some of them by MH (17) and the simple chi-square test (5). From the case-control studies that used an unmatched or frequency-matched design (8 studies), 106 ORs were computed in univariate analysis while 18 in multivariate analysis. The ORs from unmatched designs were estimated using chi-square (36) and UL (88). Bringing together the matched and

unmatched designs, 127 extracted ORs were not adjusted by any confounder (crude ORs), while only 100 ORs were adjusted using either MH or logistic regressions.

Figure 1. Flow chart of literature search for case-control studies of human listeriosis
*Records kept in JabRef with PDFs files annexed

During methodological quality assessment, the outcomes from three case-control studies were marked as being possibly biased. In Gillespie et al. (2010a), controls were not necessarily healthy people, whilst in Schlech et al. (2005), controls were patients with campylobacteriosis

or salmonellosis. Because it is not clear whether these controls shared routes of exposure with the case patients, the ORs extracted from these studies were marked as having potential for selection bias. Finally, the OR measures from Jensen et al. (1994) were assigned the potential-for-bias status because the study, in general terms, was not clearly described, and some of the ORs extracted were approximated. Those three case-control studies furnished 16 potentially-biased ORs whose influence on the pooled OR estimates was appraised by means of the Cook's distance. With regards to the risk factor classes, sporadic illness investigations focused more on the multiple pathways of transmission (168 ORs) than on host specific factors (59 ORs) (Figure 2, bottom). There was no information on risk of acquiring listeriosis through travel. General information on the distribution of the number of ORs available for meta-analysis is presented in Figure 3 by study design, type of analysis, model, type of odds-ratio, study period and potential for bias status.

Figure 2. Distribution of the number of odds-ratios (y-axis) extracted from case-control studies of sporadic human listeriosis by country of case-control study (top left), population type (bottom left) and type of risk factor (bottom right)

Figure 3. Pie-diagrams of the number of odds-ratios extracted from case-control studies of sporadic listeriosis by design (top left), analysis type (top right), model type (middle left), odds-ratio type (middle right), study period – cutoff year 2000 (bottom left) and assigned potential for bias (bottom right)

Table 1. Characteristics of case-control studies investigating sources of sporadic human listeriosis included in the meta-analysis

Study ID	Country	Study period	Population	Design	Analysis & model*	# cases/controls	Quality #ORs
Dalton et al. 2011	Australia	2001-2004	Non-perinat (immuno-compromised)	Matched	Uni-CL Multi-CL	117 cases 85 controls	Good 72
			Peri-natal	Matched	Uni-UL Multi-UL	19 cases 12 controls	
Fernández et al. 2009	Spain	1995-2007	Non-perinatal (transplant-recipients)	Matched	Uni-Chi Multi-CL	30 cases 60 controls	Good 8
Friesema et al. 2015	Netherlands	2008-2013	Non-perinatal (immuno-compromised)	Unmatched	Uni-UL Multi-UL	279 cases 1733 controls	Good 20
Gillespie et al. 2010a	UK	2001-2007	Peri/non-peri	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	171 cases 60646 controls	Poor 8
			Non-perinatal (elderly)	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	104 cases 15177 controls	
Gillespie et al. 2010b	UK	2005-2008	Non-perinatal (Elderly)	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	159 cases 18115 controls	Good 19
Jensen et al. 1994	Denmark	1989-1990	Peri/non-peri (pregnant and immunocom)	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	66 cases 33 controls	Poor 3
Linnan et al. 1988	USA	1985-1987	Peri/non-peri	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	? cases ? controls	Good 1
Preussel et al. 2015	Germany	2012-2013	Non-perinatal (Immunocom)	Unmatched	Uni-UL Multi-UL	109 cases 1982 controls	Good 36
Schlech et al. 2005	Canada	2002-2004	Non-perinatal (Underlying GI diseases)	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	12 cases 24 cases	Poor 6**
Schuchat et al. 1992	USA	1988-1990	Peri/non-peri (pregnant and immunocom)	Matched	Uni-MH Multi-CL	165 cases 376 controls	Good 13
Schwartz et al. 1988	USA	1986-1987	Peri/non-peri (pregnant and immunocom)	Matched	Uni-MH Multi-CL	80 cases 239 controls	Good 10
Varma et al. 2007	USA	2000-2003	Peri/non-peri (pregnant and immunocom)	Unmatched (frequency-matched)	Uni-UL Multi-UL	169 cases 376 controls	Good 32

(*) Univariate analysis can be univariate (Uni) and multivariate (Model) while model can be chi-square (Chi), Mantel-Haenzel (MH), unconditional logistic (UL) and conditional logistic (CL)

(**) Later on, one OR < 0.5 (exposure to antibiotics) was removed from the analysis

3.5.2 *Meta-analysis for host-specific risk factors and environment-, animal- and food-related pathways of transmission*

In none of the pathways of exposure under study, there was an effect of study period on their associations with listeriosis. Because the ORs measuring association of listeriosis with host-specific factors ($p=0.253$; Table 2B) and overall consumption of foods ($p=0.764$; Table 4B), meat ($p=0.604$; Table 5B), dairy ($p=0.767$; Table 6B), produce ($p=0.578$; Table 7B), composite meals ($p=0.832$; Table 9B) and RTE foods ($p=0.902$; Table 10B), quantified after the year 2000, did not differ significantly from those estimated in earlier case-control studies (before 2000), the variable “study period” was dropped from the full meta-analysis models in all of the aforementioned data partitions. Thus, all the pooled ORs estimated for listeriosis, presented in this report, were computed using data from both study periods.

No information was found for travel, animal-related pathways and person-to-person contagion as potential risk factors for listeriosis among the case-control studies considered for inclusion in this meta-analysis. The meta-analysis on host-specific factors by region showed that, chronic diseases, immune disorders and use of medication exacerbated the risk of acquiring listeriosis in all of the geographical regions with pooled ORs between 1.930 and 5.607, all of them associated with highly significant p -values ($p<.001$ in Table 2A). Most of the data on host-specific risk factors were extracted from Western European studies (47 ORs). The meta-analysis of these data summarised that the susceptible population people from Spain, Germany and the Netherlands who suffered from chronic diseases, autoimmune disorders and, generally, in receipt of treatments that weaken the immune system, had 4.375 times (95% CI: 3.557 – 5.376) greater probability of becoming infected with *L. monocytogenes* than those who did not (Table 2A). Putting the data from all regions together, the pooled OR for host-specific factors increases to 5.501 (95% CI: 4.003 – 7.569; Table 2B). As the associations between host-specific factors and listeriosis were equally significant across regions, all geographical regions were maintained for the full meta-analysis by subcategory.

The meta-analysis by host-specific subcategories revealed that suffering from a chronic disease was the most important predisposing factor for listeriosis among the susceptible population (i.e., perinatal and non-perinatal) at an overall OR=7.516 (95% CI: 4.568 – 12.35; Table 2B). Chronic diseases encompass cancer, chronic liver/kidney disease, organ transplant, diabetes, arthritis and rheumatism. A significantly lower association with listeriosis, yet still highly significant, was encountered for the group of other medical conditions (overall OR=5.766; 95% CI: 3.854 – 8.619). Other medical conditions included cardiovascular diseases, pre-existing liver disease, previous hospitalisation, gastrointestinal diseases, lung diseases, radiation therapy, and use of immunosuppressants, drugs other than steroids, prednisone and laxatives. On meta-analysis, susceptible people infected with listeriosis were more likely to have recently used antiacids (overall OR=4.007; 95% CI: 2.540 – 6.328) than susceptible people free of disease. For the exposure through antibiotics, the meta-analysed OR (overall OR=5.579; 95% CI: 1.835 – 16.98) was based only on two extracted ORs, reason as to why it lacks generalisability and must be interpreted with caution. The pooled OR belonging to recent use of antibiotics did not differ statistically from the other host-specific factors (Table 2B). In the host-specific factors data partition, publication bias was not evident either through the non-significant effect of study size on the measured ORs ($p=0.362$), or the scattered distribution of residuals within the funnel plot (Figure 4).

Table 2A. Meta-analyses of host specific factors for listeriosis in the combined non-perinatal (n=59) and peri/non-perinatal (n=8) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All susceptible					
North America	0.657	0.162	7	[0.340 – 0.975]	<.0001
North Europe	1.724	0.596	2	[0.556 – 2.892]	0.004
Oceania	0.915	0.219	11	[0.486 – 1.344]	<.0001
West Europe	1.476	0.105	47	[1.269 – 1.682]	<.0001

Table 2B. Meta-analysis of host specific factors for listeriosis in the combined non-perinatal (n=59) and peri/non-perinatal (n=8) population – no geographical region removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All susc	All host-specific	1.705	0.163		[1.387 – 2.024]	<.0001
(8 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Antiacids	1.388 ^a	0.233	9	[0.932 – 1.845]	<.0001
	Antibiotics	1.719 ^{abc}	0.567	2	[0.607 – 2.832]	0.003
	Chronic	2.017 ^c	0.254	22	[1.519 – 2.514]	<.0001
	Other med	1.752 ^b	0.205	34	[1.349 – 2.154]	<.0001
	UniOR	-0.564	0.115		[-0.789 - -0.337]	<.0001
	Before 2000					0.253
	Random effects					
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.1645	QE(df=62)		QM(df=4)	
	s ² (residual)	1.1995	p<.0001		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	-0.0001	0.0002			0.362
	Points removed	0				

Figure 4. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of host-specific factors for listeriosis in the combined non-perinatal and peri/non-perinatal population

Regarding the environmental-related pathways of transmission for listeriosis, very few ORs (#9) could be recovered from the literature, and they were related to living on a farm and attending/living in day care centre. Seemingly, the environmental exposures assessed in the studies from USA (pooled OR=8.339; $p=0.002$) presented overall a stronger association with listeriosis than comparable exposures investigated in the Australian study (pooled OR=1.621; $p=0.315$; Table 3A). When the general meta-analysis model was fitted, it was found that the joint environmental pathways constituted an important source of listeriosis, with an overall OR=3.186 (95% CI: 1.060 – 9.574; Table 3B). Detaching the contribution of the two ORs belonging to day care (non significant $p=0.218$), the general meta-analysis model elucidated that living in a town/rural area or on a cattle farm (overall OR=3.293; 95% CI: 1.046 – 10.38) was a major determinant of listeriosis in the susceptible population. The non-significant QE statistic implied that subgrouping environmental pathways could account for most of the variability in ORs between case-control studies. Both the formal test for publication bias ($p=0.038$; Table 3B) and the funnel plot (Figure 5) suggested that publication bias is likely.

Table 3A. Meta-analysis of pathways related to environmental pathways for listeriosis by region in the combined non-perinatal ($n=3$), perinatal ($n=3$) and peri/non-perinatal ($n=3$) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All susceptible					
North America (USA)	2.121	0.678	3	[0.792 – 3.450]	0.002
Oceania (Australia)	0.483	0.481	6	[-0.460 – 1.426]	0.315

Table 3B. Meta-analyses of pathways related to environmental pathways for listeriosis in the combined non-perinatal (n=3), perinatal (n=3) and peri/non-perinatal (n=3) population – no geographical region was removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All susc	All environment	1.159	0.561		[0.058 – 2.259]	0.039
(2 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Day care	1.013 ^a	0.823	2	[-0.600 – 2.625]	0.218
	Farm	1.192 ^a	0.586	7	[0.045 – 2.340]	0.042
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.2331	QE(df=7)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2 (residual)	1.3454	p=0.627		p=0.094	
	Publication bias	-0.0054	0.0026			0.038
	Points removed	0				

Figure 5. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of environmental pathways for listeriosis in the combined non-perinatal, perinatal and peri/non-perinatal population

Most of the routes of transmission of listeriosis recovered in the systematic review were related to consumption of contaminated food, for which a total of 141 OR measures were extracted and categorised. For the food pathways of exposure, apart from the meta-analysis models adjusted to all of the data (i.e., joining perinatal, non-perinatal and peri/non-perinatal; referred to as *all susceptible* in the summary tables), separate meta-analysis models were fitted to the *non-perinatal* population subset (n=75) for comparison. In the general susceptible population, listeriosis was greatly associated to the ingestion of contaminated foods in the case-control studies from North America (pooled OR=1.451; p<.0001) and Northern Europe (pooled OR=1.809; p<.0001; Table 4A). By contrast, the association between listeriosis and consumption of food was weak or non-significant in the susceptible population from Western Europe (pooled OR=1.239; p=0.254) and Australia (pooled OR=1.091; p=0.664). When the

meta-analysis by geographical region was undertaken on the non-perinatal population only, the pooled ORs exhibited the same tendency: higher association of listeriosis and food consumption was found for the American (pooled OR=1.648) and Northern European (pooled OR=1.383) while the lowest corresponded to Oceania (pooled OR=1.083). Nevertheless, for the general meta-analysis on the foods data partition, no geographical region was removed. If the Australian study (Oceania region), which presented the lowest pooled ORs, had been removed, the amount of meta-analytical data for the analysis of food pathways would have been reduced in 37% (Table 4A).

Table 4A. Meta-analyses of food pathways for listeriosis by region in the general susceptible (n=141) and non-perinatal population (n=75).

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All susceptible					
North America	0.372	0.107	46	[0.161 – 0.583]	<.0001
North Europe	0.593	0.136	26	[0.326 – 0.859]	<.0001
Oceania	0.087	0.200	52	[-0.304 – 0.477]	0.664
West Europe*	-	-	17	-	-
Non-perinatal					
North America	0.500	0.468	4	[-0.417 – 1.418]	0.285
North Europe	0.324	0.176	22	[-0.022 – 0.671]	0.070
Oceania	0.080	0.242	32	[-0.395 – 0.555]	0.742
West Europe	0.214	0.189	17	[-0.154 – 0.583]	0.254

(*) All data for Western Europe belonged to the non-perinatal population, so the estimates for this region are presented in the respective population group

On meta-analysis, the general susceptible population, consisting of elderly, immunocompromised people and pregnant women were slightly more predisposed to acquiring listeriosis (overall OR=1.626; 95% CI: 1.362 – 1.939) than the non-perinatal population (overall OR=1.395; 95% CI: 1.080 – 1.802), which was restricted to elderly and immunocompromised people (Table 4B). Among the food subcategories for which OR data were available (i.e., composite foods, dairy, meat, produce and seafood), produce exhibited the lowest association with listeriosis in the general susceptible population: susceptible people who ate fruits and vegetables presented on average 1.244 times (95% CI: 0.910 – 1.702) greater probability of becoming infected with listeriosis than those who did not. A significantly higher association with listeriosis in the general susceptible population was found for the consumption of meat (overall OR=1.396; 95% CI: 1.051 – 1.855), which were mainly composed of processed meats. At a significantly higher association with disease laid the category of composite foods – encompassing dishes eaten out or food bought from deli counters – at an overall OR of 1.649 (95% CI: 1.115 – 2.421) in the general susceptible population. Dairy foods and seafood were the most relevant food categories acting a vehicle of transmission of listeriosis (Table 4B). On average, susceptible people with listeriosis were 1.864 times (95% CI: 1.405 – 2.474) more likely to have consumed dairy foods than control cases; although a higher level of association with listeriosis was found for the seafood

category whereby, on average, ill patient were 2.418 times (95% CI: 1.567 – 3.732) more likely to have eaten seafood than susceptible people free of disease. When only, the non-perinatal population was meta-analysed, the same tendency was obtained. This is, the produce category had the lowest overall OR (0.986; 95% CI: 0.611 – 1.592), followed by meat (overall OR=1.201; 95% CI: 0.796 – 1.811) and composite foods (overall OR=1.237; 95% CI: 0.615 – 2.494), while dairy foods (overall OR=1.706; 95% CI: 1.093 – 2.659) and seafood (overall OR=2.377; 95% CI: 1.331 – 4.250; Table 4B) were the most important vehicles of transmission of listeriosis in the non-perinatal population.

Table 4B. Meta-analyses of food pathways for listeriosis in the general susceptible (n=141) and non-perinatal (n=75) population– no geographical region removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All susc (10 stud)	All foods	0.486	0.090		[0.309 – 0.662]	<.0001
	Fixed effects					
	Composite	0.500 ^c	0.198	10	[0.109 – 0.884]	0.012
	Dairy	0.623 ^d	0.145	45	[0.340 – 0.906]	<.0001
	Meat	0.334 ^b	0.145	44	[0.050 – 0.618]	0.021
	Produce	0.219 ^a	0.160	27	[-0.094 – 0.532]	0.170
	Seafood	0.883 ^e	0.222	15	[0.449 – 1.317]	<.0001
	Before 2000					0.764
	Random effects					
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.1738	QE(df=136)		QM(df=5)	
	s ² (residual)	0.5620	p<.0001		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	-0.0019	0.0003			<.0001
	Points removed	0				
	Non-Peri (5 stud)	All foods	0.333	0.131		[0.077 – 0.589]
Fixed effects						
Composite		0.213 ^a	0.356	4	[-0.486 – 0.914]	0.550
Dairy		0.534 ^b	0.227	27	[0.089 – 0.978]	0.018
Meat		0.183 ^a	0.209	24	[-0.228 – 0.594]	0.384
Produce		-0.014 ^a	0.244	11	[-0.492 – 0.465]	0.956
Seafood		0.866 ^c	0.296	9	[0.286 – 1.447]	0.003
Before 2000						ND
Random effects						
s ² _u (Intercept)		0.2094	QE(df=70)		QM(df=5)	
s ² (residual)		0.5066	p<.0001		p=0.010	
Publication bias		-0.0000	0.0000			0.892
Points removed		0				

Interestingly, within food categories, the pooled ORs for the non-perinatal population were consistently lower than those of the general susceptible population. Pregnant women may be more susceptible to acquiring listeriosis through consumption of contaminated food than the non-perinatal population, and hence their inclusion in the general susceptible population increased all the pooled measures of association of foods with disease. After Cook's distance assessment, no potentially-biased OR popped up as an influential point in any of the meta-analyses (Table 4B). Nevertheless, in the general susceptible population, there was a strong effect of study size on the researchers' quantification of ORs ($p < .0001$). This signifies that it is very likely that some case-control studies which did not find significant association between food exposures and listeriosis may have remained unpublished. For the population subset of non-perinatal population, however, there was no evidence of a file-drawer problem, as suggested by both the non-significant publication bias test ($p = 0.892$) and the well-behaved spread of observations within the funnel area (Figure 6, right).

Figure 6. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of food pathways for listeriosis in the general susceptible (left) and non-perinatal (right) population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Meta-analysis evidenced that listeriosis could be transmitted through the consumption of meat and meat products in the general susceptible population, particularly in Northern Europe (pooled OR=1.311; $p < .0001$) and Western Europe (pooled OR=1.314; $p = 0.008$) and, to a lesser extent, in North America (pooled OR=1.150; $p = 0.134$ in Table 5A). The meta-analysis on the 19 meat-related pathways of exposure from the only case-control study conducted in Oceania (Australia; Dalton et al., 2011) did not find any association between listeriosis and meat either in the general susceptible population (pooled OR=0.855; $p = 0.260$) or in the non-perinatal population (pooled OR=0.846; $p = 0.244$). Thus, as the OR data pertaining to meat extracted from Dalton et al. (2011) produced opposite outcomes to those from the other three geographical regions, they were removed from the meat data partition for the subsequent general meta-analysis by subcategory.

Table 5A. Meta-analyses of meat consumption related pathways for listeriosis by region in the general susceptible (n=44) and non-perinatal (n=24) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All susceptible					
North America	0.140	0.093	13	[-0.041 – 0.323]	0.134
North Europe	0.271	0.070	7	[0.130 – 0.408]	<.0001
Oceania	-0.157	0.139	19	[-0.431 – 0.116]	0.260
West Europe*	-	-	5	-	-
Non-perinatal					
North America	0.431	0.510	2	[-0.568 – 1.431]	0.397
North Europe	0.239	0.075	6	[0.092 – 0.386]	0.001
Oceania	-0.167	0.144	11	[-0.448 – 0.114]	0.244
West Europe	0.273	0.102	5	[0.072 – 0.474]	0.008

(*) All data for Western Europe belonged to the non-perinatal population, so the estimates for this region are presented in the respective population group

Within meats, red meats including beef, pork, BBQ meat and hamburger bore the lowest – if any – risk of transmission of listeriosis in the general susceptible population at a non-significant overall OR of 0.989 (95% CI: 0.809 – 1.208 in Table 5B). A significantly higher association with disease in the susceptible population was found for processed meats, which were made up of processed pork, processed poultry, cooked sausages, raw fermented spreadable sausages, dry-cured ham, deli meats, hotdogs, pate, cold meats and uncooked hotdogs. On meta-analysis, susceptible people who consumed any of the aforementioned processed meats presented 1.385 times (95% CI: 1.127 – 1.701) greater probability of acquiring listeriosis than those who did not. Undercooked poultry meat bore the highest association with listeriosis at a pooled OR of 1.976 (95% CI: 1.532 – 2.544; Table 5B); although it should be kept in mind that only 5 ORs were available for this pathway of exposure. Meta-analysis on the non-perinatal population showed again that red meats do not appear to act as vehicles of listeriosis (overall OR=1.005; p=0.967). Moreover, as observed in the general susceptible population, in the non-perinatal population the consumption of processed meats represented an important pathway of exposure to listeriosis (overall OR=1.532; 95% CI: 1.226 – 1.914). In both of the meta-analyses – general susceptible (p=0.003) and non-perinatal population (p=0.103; Table 5B), the quantification of OR depended upon the size of the case-control study. Though, their corresponding funnel plots did not evidence strong publication bias (Figure 7).

In the questionnaires presented to cases and controls, previous consumption of eggs, beverages and grains was seldom enquired. For this reason, meta-analyses could not be conducted on the above subcategories.

Table 5B. Meta-analyses of meat consumption related pathways for listeriosis in the general susceptible (n=25) and non-perinatal (n=13) population – Oceania removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All susc (7 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Red meats	-0.011 ^a	0.102	7	[-0.211 – 0.189]	0.915
	Undercook poultry	0.681 ^c	0.130	5	[0.427 – 0.934]	<.0001
	Proc meat	0.326 ^b	0.105	13	[0.120 – 0.531]	0.002
	Before 2000					0.490
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0226	QE(df=22)		QM(df=3)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.6298	p<.0001		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	-0.0000	0.0000			0.003
	Points removed	0				
Non-peri (4 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Red meats	0.005 ^a	0.114	6	[-0.219 – 0.228]	0.967
	Proc meat	0.427 ^b	0.114	7	[0.204 – 0.649]	<.0001
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0121	QE(df=11)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.2656	p<.0001		p=0.001	
	Publication bias	0.0000	0.0000			0.103
	Points removed	0				

Figure 7. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of meat consumption pathways for listeriosis in the general susceptible (left) and non-perinatal (right) population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

The meta-analysis on dairy pathways of transmission by geographical region showed that in North America (pooled OR=1.774; p=0.001), Northern Europe (pooled OR=1.872; p=0.024) and Oceania (pooled OR=1.752; p=0.091), these products are potential determinants of listeriosis in the general susceptible population, and, to a comparable level of association, in the non-perinatal susceptible population from Northern Europe (pooled OR=1.758, p<.0001) and Oceania (pooled OR=1.763; p=0.003). A lower overall association between dairy products and listeriosis, yet still significant (p=0.067), was observed in the Western European susceptible non-perinatal population (pooled OR=1.165 in Table 6A).

Table 6A. Meta-analyses of dairy consumption related pathways for listeriosis by region in the general susceptible (n=45) and non-perinatal (n=26) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All susceptible					
North America	0.573	0.171	16	[0.237 – 0.909]	0.001
North Europe	0.627	0.277	10	[0.084 – 1.170]	0.024
Oceania	0.561	0.332	11	[-0.090 – 1.211]	0.091
West Europe*	-	-	8	-	-
Non-perinatal					
North Europe	0.564	0.067	9	[0.432 – 0.696]	<.0001
Oceania	0.567	0.189	9	[0.197 – 0.938]	0.003
West Europe	0.153	0.083	8	[-0.011 – 0.316]	0.067

(*) All data for Western Europe belonged to the non-perinatal population, so the estimates for this region are presented in the respective population group

The general meta-analysis by subcategory highlighted that the consumption of cheese by the general susceptible population (overall OR=2.807; 95% CI: 1.931 – 4.129) and the specific non-perinatal population (overall OR=2.942; 95% CI: 1.861 – 4.651) posed a very high risk of listeriosis (Table 6B). The cheese category comprised Mexican cheese, feta cheese, Brie, Camembert, cream cheese, blue-veined cheese, pre-sliced and packaged cheese, red-smear cheese, semi-soft cheese, ricotta, mozzarella and white mould cheese. However, the consumption of milk and fats bore a greater risk of disease: while susceptible people who consumed raw milk, cream and butter presented overall 3.251 (95% CI: 2.069 – 5.114) times higher odds of becoming ill than those who did not; the non-perinatal group presented a comparable risk of listeriosis (overall OR=3.307; 95% CI: 1.976 – 5.534; Table 6B) from the consumption of raw milk and dairy fats. In both of the meta-analyses, there was no evidence of publication bias by the formal test (Table 6B). Furthermore, the spread of residuals within the funnel areas were satisfactory (Figure 8). Investigating dairy products as sources of listeriosis was usual in the case-control studies, so it is likely that the outcomes of these exposures would not have been omitted from publication.

Table 6B. Meta-analyses of dairy consumption related pathways for listeriosis in the general susceptible (n=45) and non-perinatal (n=27) population – no region removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All susc (9 st)	Fixed effects					
	Cheese	1.032 ^a	0.193	40	[0.658 – 1.418]	<.0001
	Milk&Fats	1.179 ^b	0.230	5	[0.727 – 1.632]	<.0001
	UniOR	-0.607	0.167		[-0.935 - -0.280]	<.0001
	Before 2000					0.767
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0794	QE(df=42)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.3982	p<.0001		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	0.0000	0.0000			0.662
	Points removed	0				
Non-peri (4 st)	Fixed effects					
	Cheese	1.079 ^a	0.233	24	[0.621 – 1.537]	<.0001
	Milk&Fats	1.196 ^b	0.263	3	[0.681 – 1.711]	<.0001
	UniOR	-0.741	0.199		[-1.131 - -0.351]	<.0001
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0524	QE(df=24)		QE(df=2)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.3693	p<.0001		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	0.0000	0.0000			0.130
	Points removed	0				

On average, the importance of the produce in the transmission of *L. monocytogenes* was only minor, as suggested by the non-significant associations obtained in both the general susceptible (p=0.423 – 0.640) and the non-perinatal (p=0.686 – 0.764) population across the different geographical regions (Table 7A). Pooled ORs for produce, as a whole, were weak and ranged from 0.907 to 1.167. Thus, no geographical region was removed for the subsequent general meta-analysis by produce class.

In the general susceptible and the non-perinatal population, the most innocuous class of produce, in terms of human infection with listeriosis, corresponded to vegetables (overall OR=1.104; 95% CI: 0.848 – 1.438; and overall OR=0.918; 95% CI: 0.610 – 1.381, respectively), which comprised coleslaw, lettuce, organic produce, carrots, green groceries, raw vegetables, alfalfa sprouts, mixed salads and deli salads (Table 7B). Eating fruits bore a higher risk of listeriosis in the susceptible population: on meta-analysis, susceptible people who consumed melons, cantaloupe, strawberries or RTE fruit salads had 1.570 times (95% CI: 1.060 – 2.323) greater probability of infection with listeriosis than those who did not

consumed any of those fruits. In the non-perinatal susceptible population, the level of risk from consumption of fruits (overall OR=1.539; 95% CI: 0.763 – 3.105) was as high as in the general susceptible population (Table 7B). In both the general susceptible and non-perinatal population’s meta-analyses, the observations were adequately dispersed within the funnel plots (Figure 9), therefore publication bias would not be an issue in the produce data partition.

Figure 8. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of dairy consumption related pathways for listeriosis in the general susceptible (left) and non-perinatal population (right). Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table 7A. Meta-analyses of produce consumption related pathways for listeriosis by region in the general susceptible (n=27) and non-perinatal (n=10) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All susceptible					
North America	0.155	0.194	8	[-0.224 – 0.534]	0.423
North Europe	0.123	0.186	4	[-0.241 – 0.487]	0.508
Oceania	0.149	0.319	15	[-0.476 – 0.775]	0.640
Non-perinatal					
Europe	-0.097	0.240	3	[-0.567 – 0.373]	0.686
Oceania	0.120	0.400	7	[-0.664 – 0.905]	0.764

Table 7B. Meta-analyses of produce consumption related pathways for listeriosis in the general susceptible (n=27) and non-perinatal (n=11) population – no region removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All susc (7 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Fruits	0.451 ^b	0.200	11	[0.059 – 0.843]	0.024
	Vegetables	0.099 ^a	0.135	16	[-0.165 – 0.363]	0.463
	Before 2000					0.578
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0742	QE(df=25)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.2075	p=0.001		p=0.060	
	Publication bias	0.0000	0.0001			0.001
	Points removed	0				
	Non-peri (5 stud)	Fixed effects				
Fruits		0.431 ^a	0.358	3	[-0.270 – 1.133]	0.228
Vegetables		-0.085 ^a	0.208	8	[-0.494 – 0.323]	0.682
Before 2000						ND
Random effects						
s^2_u (Intercept)		0.1298	QE(df=9)		QM(df=2)	
s^2 (residual)		0.1708	p=0.011		p=0.315	
Publication bias		0.0000	0.0000			0.055
Points removed		0				

Figure 9. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of produce consumption related pathways for listeriosis in the general susceptible (left) and non-perinatal (right) population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

The meta-analysis on the seafood data partition suggested that among the Northern European susceptible population (pooled OR=5.053; $p < .0001$), seafood was much more important a

vehicle of listeriosis than in North America (pooled OR=1.377; p=0.259) and Australia (pooled OR=0.905; p=0.905; Table 8A). Nonetheless, the ORs available in the literature for exposures pertaining to seafood were too few to arrive to sound conclusions. Because of the limited data, no geographical removed was removed in order to perform the general meta-analysis by subcategories.

Table 8A. Meta-analyses of seafood consumption related pathways for listeriosis by region in the combined perinatal (n=2), non-perinatal (n=9) and peri/non-perinatal (n=4) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All susceptible					
North America	0.320	0.284	3	[-0.236 – 0.876]	0.259
North Europe	1.620	0.162	5	[1.301 – 1.938]	<.0001
Oceania	-0.100	0.300	7	[-0.687 – 0.488]	0.741

On meta-analysis, crustaceans, represented by prawns, were not a significant vehicle of transmission of listeriosis (overall OR=0.911; 95% CI: 0.312 – 2.656) whereas molluscs – mussels and oysters – bore a significantly greater association with listeriosis (overall OR=2.151; 95% CI: 0.662 – 6.987; Table 8B) in the general susceptible population. The only seafood class that, on meta-analysis, was highly determinant of listeriosis was fish and smoked fish: on average, susceptible people affected by listeriosis were 2.659 times (95% CI: 1.144 – 6.184 in Table 8B) more likely to have consumed fish and smoked fish than susceptible controls.

Table 8B. Meta-analysis of seafood consumption related pathways for listeriosis in the combined perinatal (n=2), non-perinatal (n=9) and peri/non-perinatal (n=4) population – no region removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All susc						
(4 st)	Fixed effects					
	Crustaceans	-0.093 ^a	0.546	3	[-1.164 – 0.977]	0.864
	Molluscs	0.766 ^b	0.601	4	[-0.412 – 1.944]	0.202
	Processed&Fish	0.978 ^b	0.430	8	[0.135 – 1.822]	0.023
	Before 2000					ND
Random effects						
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.4005	QE(df=12)		QM(df=3)	
	s ² (residual)	0.8572	p<.0001		p=0.067	
	Publication bias	0.0000	0.0000			0.002
	Points removed	0				

A forest plot compiling the extracted ORs for fish and smoked fish is presented in Figure 10. Notice that the random-effects solution for the overall OR in the forest plot (2.62; 95% CI: 1.21 – 5.67) is slightly different from the one computed by the general meta-analysis model (2.66; 95% CI: 1.14 – 6.18; Table 8B). The difference arises from the fact that the general meta-analysis model is fitted to the *whole seafood data*, extracting the variabilities due to study and model type while incorporating the seafood subclasses as fixed effects, whereas the simpler meta-analysis model of the forest plot is fitted to one seafood class (fish/smoked fish data), extracting only the between-study variability. Both the formal test for publication bias ($p=0.002$ in Table 8B) and the funnel plot (Figure 11) suggested that some file-drawer problem is likely.

Figure 10. Forest plot of the association of listeriosis with consumption of fish and smoked fish (n=8) in the general susceptible population, as measured by the odds-ratio parameterisation

Figure 11. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of seafood consumption related pathways for listeriosis in the combined perinatal, non-perinatal and peri/non-perinatal population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Composite foods constituted an important source of listeriosis in the general susceptible population from USA (pooled OR=1.862; p=0.026 in Table 9A). By contrast, combining the very few data available from the European studies, it was found that composite foods were not strongly associated with listeriosis in the susceptible population (pooled OR=1.273; p=0.397; Table 9A). When zooming into the composite foods categories, it was found out that composite dishes, which were mostly dishes eaten outside the home, posed a higher risk of listeriosis (overall OR=1.751; 95% CI: 0.961 – 3.190) to the susceptible population than composite RTE foods (overall OR=1.425; 95% CI: 0.684 – 2.971 in Table 9B). Nonetheless, these results are to be interpreted cautiously as there was strong evidence of publication bias, as implied by the formal test (p<.0001; Table 9B) and the asymmetrical funnel plot (Figure 12). The lack of points on the left of side of the funnel suggests that there might be some low OR values from case-control studies that remained unpublished because of lack of significance.

Table 9A. Meta-analysis of composite-food related pathways for listeriosis by region in the combined non-perinatal (n=4) and peri/non-perinatal (n=6) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All susceptible					
North America	0.622	0.280	6	[0.074 – 1.170]	0.026
Europe	0.242	0.286	4	[-0.318 – 0.803]	0.397

Table 9B. Meta-analysis of composite-food related pathways for listeriosis in the combined non-perinatal (n=4) and peri/non-perinatal (n=6) population – no region was removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All susc (4 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Dishes	0.560 ^a	0.306	7	[-0.040 – 1.160]	0.067
	RTE	0.354 ^a	0.375	3	[-0.380 – 1.089]	0.344
	Before 2000					0.832
Random effects						
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.2202	QE(df=8)		QM(df=2)	
	s ² (residual)	0.4028	p=0.002		p=0.120	
	Publication bias	-0.0001	0.0000			<.0001
	Points removed	0				

Figure 12. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of composite-food pathways for listeriosis in the combined non-perinatal (n=4) and peri/non-perinatal (n=6) population

3.5.3 Meta-analysis on the risk of listeriosis by ready-to-eat foods

As a whole, RTE foods can be regarded as an important vehicle of transmission of listeriosis, as deduced from the integration of the outcomes from case-control studies undertaken in North America in the general susceptible population (pooled OR=1.542; $p=0.001$), and in Northern Europe (pooled OR=2.004; $p<.0001$) and Western Europe (pooled OR=1.183; $p=0.008$; Table 10A) in the non-perinatal susceptible population. Only, in the case-control study from Australia (Dalton et al., 2011), there was not strong evidence that RTE foods could be an important source of listeriosis in the susceptible population (pooled OR=1.186; $p=0.476$; Table 10A). The general meta-analysis conducted taking into account all geographical regions estimated that susceptible people who consumed RTE foods had, on average, 1.650 times (95% CI: 1.313 – 2.073; Table 10B) greater probability of acquiring listeriosis than those who were not exposed by consumption. The non-perinatal susceptible people bore an equivalent level of risk of listeriosis from consumption of RTE foods at an overall OR of 1.677 (95% CI: 1.142 – 2.462; Table 10B).

The meta-analyses by RTE class revealed that the produce-based RTE products were not important vehicles of transmission of listeriosis in both the general susceptible population (overall OR=1.061; 95% CI: 0.562 – 2.006) and the non-perinatal population subset (overall OR=1.052; 95% CI: 0.604 – 1.833 in Table 10B). The produce-based RTE class comprised RTE fruit salads, prepared coleslaw and mixed salads. The meat-based RTE foods presented a significantly higher level of association with listeriosis in the general susceptible (overall OR=1.216; 95% CI: 0.806 – 1.839) and the non-perinatal susceptible population (overall OR=1.328; 95% CI: 0.871 – 2.028), although in any of the cases reached statistical significance (Table 10B). A forest plot for the meat-based RTE products is shown in Figure 13, which displays the range of processed meat products that were meta-analysed. The dairy-based RTE products, overall, constituted a strong determinant of listeriosis in the general susceptible population (overall OR=1.864; 95% CI: 1.300 – 2.672) and the non-perinatal population subset (overall OR=1.669; 95% CI: 1.113 – 2.504). The forest plot of the association between dairy RTE foods and listeriosis is shown in Figure 14. Although a limited

number of ORs was available for seafood-based RTE foods, the meta-analyses on these data revealed that the consumption of contaminated seafood RTE products bears a significantly higher risk of listeriosis than the consumption of dairy RTE foods: on meta-analysis, susceptible people with listeriosis were 3.473 times (95% CI: 1.779 – 6.780) more likely to have consumed seafood RTE than those susceptible free of disease; whereas elderly and immunocompromised people who consumed any of those foodstuffs had on average 7.221 times (95% CI: 3.483 – 14.97) greater probability of acquiring listeriosis than those who did not. Despite the results of the formal test for publication bias implied that some ORs related to RTE consumption exposures remained unpublished ($p=0.012$ for the general susceptible population; and $p=0.055$ for the non-perinatal subset; Table 10B), the even spread of data points within both funnel plot suggested that such file-drawer bias would be minor (Figure 15).

Table 10A. Meta-analysis of the risk of listeriosis due to RTE foods by region in all susceptible (n=76) and non-perinatal (n=47) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All susceptible					
North America	0.433	0.130	22	[0.178 – 0.688]	0.001
North Europe*	-	-	14	-	-
Oceania	0.171	0.240	27	[-0.300 – 0.642]	0.476
West Europe*	-	-	13	-	-
Non-perinatal					
North America	0.493	0.602	2	[-0.687 – 1.673]	0.413
North Europe	0.695	0.051	14	[0.594 – 0.795]	<.0001
Oceania	0.178	0.134	18	[-0.085 – 0.441]	0.184
West Europe	0.168	0.063	13	[0.045 – 0.292]	0.008

(*) All data for Northern and Western Europe belonged to the non-perinatal population, so the estimates for these regions are tabulated in the respective population group

Table 10B. Meta-analysis of the risk of listeriosis due to consumption of RTE foods overall and by RTE category in the general susceptible (n=76) and non-perinatal (n=47) population. No geographical region was removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All susc (8 stud)	All RTE foods	0.501	0.117	76	[0.272 – 0.729]	<.0001
	Fixed effects					
	Dairy-based	0.623 ^b	0.184	41	[0.262 – 0.983]	0.001
	Meat-based	0.196 ^a	0.210	24	[-0.216 – 0.609]	0.351
	Produce-based	0.059 ^a	0.325	6	[-0.577 – 0.696]	0.855
	Seafood based	1.245 ^c	0.341	5	[0.576 – 1.914]	<.0001
	Before 2000					0.902
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.1732	QE(df=72)		QM(df=4)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.3946	p<.0001		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	0.0000	0.0000			0.012
Points removed	0					
Non-peri (4 stud)	All RTE foods	0.517	0.196	47	[0.133 – 0.901]	0.008
	Fixed effects					
	Dairy-based	0.512 ^a	0.207	24	[0.107 – 0.918]	0.013
	Meat-based	0.284 ^b	0.216	16	[-0.138 – 0.707]	0.187
	Produce-based	0.051	0.283	4	[-0.504 – 0.606]	0.857
	Seafood based	1.977	0.371	3	[1.248 – 2.706]	<.0001
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.1674	QE(df=43)		QM(df=4)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.3952	p<.0001		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	0.0000	0.0000			0.055
Points removed	0					

Figure 13. Forest plot of the association of listeriosis with consumption of RTE meat products (n=24) in the general susceptible population, as measured by the odds-ratio parameterisation

Figure 14. Forest plot of the association of listeriosis with consumption of RTE dairy products – mostly cheeses (n=41) – in the general susceptible population, as measured by the odds-ratio parameterisation

Figure 15. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of risk of listeriosis due to consumption of RTE foods in the general susceptible (left) and non-perinatal (right) population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

The main results from the meta-analyses on risk factors and routes of exposure were summarised in two forest plots: one forest plot was designed for comparing the overall associations of the *global* risk categories with listeriosis (Figure 16) and the other forest plot for comparing the global associations of the *disaggregated* pathways of exposure with the disease (Figure 17). To visually distinguish the most important routes of transmission, the pooled ORs listed in the forest plots were ranked by mean's decreasing order, and to assess the reliability in the pooled ORs, the number of ORs used in the computations were displayed.

Examining the global risk categories in the general susceptible population, the host-specific factors (overall OR=5.50; 95% CI: 4.00 – 7.56) and the environmental routes of transmission (overall OR=3.19; 95% CI: 1.06 – 9.58) were more important risk factors for acquiring listeriosis than the food consumption pathways as a whole (overall OR=1.63; 95% CI: 1.36 – 1.94; Figure 16). According to their association with listeriosis in the general susceptible population, the global food categories ranked in decreasing order were (Figure 16): seafood (overall OR=2.42; 95% CI: 1.57 – 3.93), dairy (overall OR=1.86; 95% CI: 1.40 – 2.47), RTE foods (overall OR=1.65; 95% CI: 1.31 – 2.08), composite foods (overall OR=1.65; 95% CI: 1.12 – 2.44), meat (overall OR=1.40; 95% CI: 1.05 – 1.86) and produce (overall OR=1.24; 95% CI: 0.91 – 1.70). Interestingly, in the non-perinatal susceptible population subset, the global food categories followed exactly the same ranking as in the general susceptible population, yet with pooled ORs that were slightly lower (Figure 16): seafood (overall OR=2.38; 95% CI: 1.33 – 4.25), dairy (overall OR=1.71; 95% CI: 1.09 – 2.66), RTE foods (overall OR=1.68; 95% CI: 1.14 – 2.46), composite foods (overall OR=1.24; 95% CI: 0.62 – 2.49), meat (overall OR=1.20; 95% CI: 0.80 – 1.81) and produce (overall OR=0.99; 95% CI: 0.61 – 1.59). Thus, pregnant women may be more susceptible to acquire listeriosis through the consumption of contaminated foods than elderly and immunocompromised people.

Figure 16. Forest plot summarising overall odds-ratios of acquiring listeriosis for global risk categories, ranked in decreasing order. The global risk categories presented are only those made up of at least n=4 ORs

Exploring the disaggregated risk factors (Figure 17), it became evident that, suffering from a chronic disease (overall OR=7.52; 95% CI: 4.57 – 12.35), other medical conditions (overall OR=5.77; 95% CI: 3.85 – 8.62) and recent use of antiacids (overall OR=4.01; 95% CI: 2.54 – 6.33) were the most important predisposing factors for acquiring listeriosis in the general susceptible population, followed by living on a farm/rural environment (overall OR=3.29; 95% CI: 1.05 – 10.38). In relation to the pathways of exposure related to food consumption, the food categories followed a similar ranking as sources of listeriosis in the general susceptible population and the non-perinatal subset. Among the potential food vehicles of transmission, seafood-based RTE products bore the greatest risk of listeriosis in the general susceptible population (overall OR=3.47; 95% CI: 1.78 – 6.78) and in the non-perinatal population subset (overall OR=7.22; 95% CI: 3.48 – 14.97); being significantly higher than dairy foods such as milk and dairy fats (overall OR=3.25; 95% CI: 2.07 – 5.11; and overall OR=3.31; 95% CI: 1.98 – 5.53, respectively) and cheese (overall OR=2.81; 95% CI: 1.93 –

4.12; and overall OR=2.94; 95% CI: 1.86 – 4.65, respectively). In the general susceptible population, fish and processed fish (overall OR=2.66; 95% CI: 1.14 – 6.18), molluscs (overall OR=2.15; 95% CI: 0.66 – 6.99) and undercooked poultry (overall OR=1.98; 95% CI: 1.53 – 2.54) presented on average a higher association with listeriosis than dairy-based RTE foods (overall OR=1.86; 95% CI: 1.30 – 2.67), composite dishes mostly prepared outside the home (overall OR=1.75; 95% CI: 0.96 – 3.19), and composite RTE foods (overall OR=1.42; 95% CI: 0.68 – 2.97). Interestingly, fresh fruits and salads, consumed by the general susceptible (overall OR=1.57; 95% CI: 1.06 – 2.32) and the non-perinatal population subset (overall OR=1.54; 95% CI: 0.76 – 3.10), emerged as a vehicle of transmission of listeriosis, at least as important as processed meats (overall OR=1.39; 95% CI: 1.13 – 1.70; and overall OR=1.53; 95% CI: 1.23 – 1.91, respectively) and meat-based RTE products (overall OR=1.22; 95% CI: 0.81 – 1.84; and overall OR=1.33; 95% CI: 0.87 – 2.03, respectively) (Figure 17).

The food pathways of exposure that on meta-analysis had either weak (pooled OR marginally higher than one) or non-significant association with listeriosis were common to the general susceptible population and the non-perinatal susceptible population. Those were (Figure 17): vegetables (overall OR=1.10; 95% CI: 0.85 – 1.44; and overall OR=0.92; 95% CI: 0.61 – 1.38, respectively), red meats (overall OR=0.99; 95% CI: 0.81 – 1.21; and overall OR=1.01; 95% CI: 0.80 – 1.26, respectively), produce-based RTE foods (overall OR=1.06; 95% CI: 0.56 – 2.01; and overall OR=1.05; 95% CI: 0.60 – 1.83, respectively) and crustaceans (overall OR=0.91; 95% CI: 0.31 – 2.66).

3.5.4 *Meta-analysis on the effects of handling and setting on the risk of transmission of listeriosis by food consumption*

For some food classes, for which relevant information was available, the effects of handling and setting were appraised. The data partitions suitable for this analysis were: (i) processed meats and poultry, and (ii) fruits. Full estimates and funnel plots are shown in the supplementary Tables S1-S2 and Figures S1-S2. As in previous findings on the effects of setting on sporadic salmonellosis and campylobacteriosis, eating out came up as a significant factor increasing the risk of listeriosis infection. On average, susceptible people who had consumed fruits and became ill were 2.358 times (95% CI: 1.297 – 3.622 in Table 11) more likely to have that prepared in a food establishment than those who consumed fruits but did not get ill. On meta-analysis, susceptible people who affirmed having eaten raw processed meats or undercooked poultry had 2.168 times (95% CI: 1.297 – 3.622) greater probability of acquiring listeriosis than those who stated having consumed *simply* processed meats or poultry (Table 11).

Table 11. Meta-analysed effects of handling and setting on base ORs by relevant food class

Food class	Estimate	Mean	2.5 th pct	97.5 th pct
Processed meat & poultry (n=35)	OR(Base)	2.311	1.370	3.904
	OR(Undercooked or Raw)/OR(Base)	2.168	1.297	3.622
Fruits (n=11)	OR(Base)	1.063	0.719	4.302
	OR(EatingOut)/OR(Base)	2.358	1.483	3.751

Figure 17. Forest plot summarising overall odds-ratios of acquiring listeriosis for disaggregated risk categories, ranked in decreasing order. The disaggregated risk categories presented are only those made up of at least n=3 ORs

4 Conclusions

4.5 Meta-analysis on risk factors for sporadic listeriosis

- ❖ The outcomes from 12 case-control studies investigating routes of exposure for sporadic human listeriosis were meta-analysed within relevant risk factors and routes of transmission, taking into account geographical region and period of study.
- ❖ The top three determinants of listeriosis in the general susceptible population are all related to host-specific factors: chronic disease (OR=7.52), other medical conditions (OR=5.77) and recent use of antiacids (OR=4.01)
- ❖ In the general susceptible population, living on a farm bear (OR=3.29) greater risk of transmission of listeriosis than the overall routes of exposure related to food consumption (OR=1.63).
- ❖ Among the food subcategories, seafood-based RTE products bear the greatest association with listeriosis in the general susceptible population (OR=3.47) and in the non-perinatal subset (OR=7.22), being significantly higher than dairy foods such as milk and dairy fats (OR=3.25 and 3.31, respectively) and cheese (OR=2.81 and 2.94, respectively).
- ❖ Fish and processed fish (OR=2.66), molluscs (OR=2.15) and undercooked poultry (OR=1.98) are, as a whole, more determinant of listeriosis than dairy-based RTE foods (OR=1.86), composite dishes mostly eaten out (OR=1.75), and composite RTE foods (OR=1.42).
- ❖ Fresh fruits and salads, consumed by the general susceptible population (OR=1.57) and the non-perinatal subset (OR=1.54), emerged as a vehicle of transmission of listeriosis, at least as important as processed meats (OR=1.39 and 1.53, respectively) and meat-based RTE products (OR=1.22 and 1.33, respectively)
- ❖ The food pathways of exposure that on meta-analysis had weak or non-significant association with listeriosis were common to the general susceptible population and the non-perinatal susceptible population. Those were: vegetables (OR=0.92 - 1.10), red meats (OR=0.99 - 1.01), produce-based RTE foods (OR=1.05 - 1.06) and crustaceans (OR=0.91).
- ❖ Very limited or no data were available for travel, animal-contact, person-to-person, and food subcategories such as eggs, grains and beverages, so the significance of these sources as potential vehicles of transmission of listeriosis could not be appraised.
- ❖ Susceptible people who had consumed fruits and acquire listeriosis were 2.36 times more likely to have that served in a food establishment than those who consumed fruits but did not get ill.

- ❖ Susceptible people who affirmed having eaten raw processed meats or undercooked poultry had 2.17 times greater probability of acquiring listeriosis than those who stated having consumed *simply* processed meats or poultry.

5 References

5.3 Twelve case-control studies for *L. monocytogenes*

[Dalton et al., 2011] Dalton, C. B., Merritt, T. D., Unicomb, L. E., Kirk, M. D., Stafford, R. J., Lalor, K., and Grp, O. W. (2011). A national case-control study of risk factors for listeriosis in Australia. *Epidemiology and Infection*, 139(3):437–445.

[FernándezSabé et al., 2009] Fernández Sabé, N., Cervera, C., López Medrano, F., Llano, M., Sáez, E., Len, O., Fortún, J., Blenes, M., Laporta, R., Torre Cisneros, J., Gavaldà, J., Muñoz, P., Fariñas, M., Aguado, J., Moreno, A., and Carratalà, J. (2009). Risk factors, clinical features, and outcomes of listeriosis in solid-organ transplant recipients: a matched case-control study. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*, 49(8):1153–1159.

[Friesema et al., 2015] Friesema, I. H., Kuiling, S., van der Ende, A., Heck, M. E., Spanjaard, L., and van Pelt, W. (2015). Risk factors for sporadic listeriosis in the Netherlands, 2008 to 2013. *Eurosurveillance*, 20(31):15–19.

[Gillespie et al., 2010a] Gillespie, I. A., Mook, P., Little, C. L., Grant, K. A., and McLauchlin, J. (2010a). Human listeriosis in England, 2001-2007: Association with neighbourhood deprivation. *Eurosurveillance*, 15(27):7–16.

[Gillespie et al., 2010b] Gillespie, I. A., Mook, P., Little, C. L., Grant, K., and Adak, G. K. (2010b). *Listeria monocytogenes* infection in the over-60s in England between 2005 and 2008: A retrospective case-control study utilizing market research panel data. *Foodborne Pathogens and Disease*, 7(11):1373–1379.

[Jensen, 1994] Jensen, A., Wilhelm Frederiksen, and Peter Gerner-Smidt. (1994). Risk factors for listeriosis in Denmark, 1989-1990. *Scandinavian Journal of Infectious Diseases*, pages 171–178.

[Linnan et al., 1988] Linnan, M., Mascola, L., Lou, X. D., Goulet, V., May, S., Salminen, C., Hird, D., Yonekura, M., Hayes, P., Weaver, R., Audurier, A., Plikaytis, B., Fannin, S., Kleks, A., and Broome, C. (1988). Epidemic listeriosis associated with Mexican-style cheese. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 319(13):823–828.

[Preußel et al., 2015] Preußel, K., Milde-Busch, A., Schmich, P., Wetzstein, M., Stark, K., and Werber, D. c. (2015). Risk factors for sporadic non-pregnancy associated listeriosis in

Germany-immunocompromised patients and frequently consumed ready-to-eat products. *PLoS ONE*, 10(11).

[Schlech III et al., 2005] Schlech III, W., Schlech IV, W., Haldane, H., Mailman, T., Warhuus, M., Grouse, N., and Haldane, D. (2005). Does sporadic *Listeria* gastroenteritis exist? A 2-year population-based survey in Nova Scotia, Canada. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*, 41(6):778–784.

[Schuchat et al., 1992] Schuchat, A., Deaver, K. A. and Wenger, J. D., Plikaytis, B. D., Mascola, L., Pinner, R. W., Reingold, A. L., and Broome, C. V. (1992). Role of foods in sporadic listeriosis. 1. Case-control study of dietary risk-factors. *JAMA-Journal of American Medical Association*, 267(15):2041–2045.

[Schwartz et al., 1988] Schwartz, B., Broome, C., Brown, G., Hightower, A., Ciesielski, C., Gaventa, S., Gellin, B., Mascola, L., and Group, L. S. (1988). Association of sporadic listeriosis with consumption of uncooked hot dogs and undercooked chicken. *The Lancet*, 332(8614):779–782.

[Varma et al., 2007] Varma, J., Samuel, M., Marcus, R., Hoekstra, R., Medus, C., Segler, S., Anderson, B., Jones, T., Shiferaw, B., Haubert, N., Megginson, M., McCarthy, P., Graves, L., Van Gilder, T., and Angulo, F. (2007). *Listeria monocytogenes* infection from foods prepared in a commercial establishment: A case-control study of potential sources of sporadic illness in the United States. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*, 44(4):521–528.

3 Supplementary tables and figures of the effects of handling and setting on the transmission of listeriosis

Table S1. Meta-analysis on the effect of handling on the risk of listeriosis by consumption of processed meat (n=26) and poultry (n=7) [7 studies]

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Fixed effects					
Handl: Base	0.838	0.267	26	[0.315 – 1.362]	0.002
Handl: Raw or undercook	0.774	0.262	7	[0.260 – 1.287]	0.003
Uni	-0.725	0.247		[-1.210 – -0.241]	0.003
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0522				
s^2 (residual)	0.4870				
Publication bias	0.0000	0.000			0.070
Points removed	0				

Figure S1. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis on the effect of handling on the risk of listeriosis by consumption of processed meat and poultry. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table S2. Meta-analysis on the effect of setting on the risk of listeriosis by consumption of fruits (n=11) [2 studies]

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Fixed effects					
Setting: Base	0.061	0.132	8	[-0.330 – 1.459]	0.645
Setting: Eating Out	0.858	0.237	3	[0.394 – 1.322]	<.0001
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=9)			
s^2 (residual)	0.2265	p=0.745			
Publication bias	-0.0014	0.0008			0.077
Points removed	0				

Figure S2. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis on the effect of setting on the risk of listeriosis by consumption of fruits